

THE PROJECT

There is a great variety of mushrooms in the city of Coimbra. The "Mushrooms in the City" project aims to help citizens identify and enjoy the mushrooms that live among us. By sharing your observations on the Biodiversity4All platform through the iNaturalist app you can count on a community of naturalists from all around the world to help you name your findings.

WHAT IS A MUSHROOM?

When we come across a mushroom, the organism we are studying - the fungus - is actually immersed in the substrate, such as wood or the soil beneath our feet. Most fungi are made up of a network of filaments known as mycelium (other fungi, like yeasts, are unicellular). When the environmental conditions are suitable, the fungus develops a reproductive structure commonly known as the mushroom, which releases spores and enables the formation of new individuals.

WHY REGISTER YOUR OBSERVATIONS?

Fungi play very important roles in ecosystems, including in cities, but their diversity remains poorly known. By recording your observations on the platform, you will learn to recognise some species and will contribute to our scientific work. There are mushrooms with a wide range of shapes, colours, and sizes. You will be surprised by what you can find!

Visit us on instagram (@cfe_micolab) !

Text: Susana P. Cunha and Susana C. Gonçalves
Design and Photographs: Susana P. Cunha

CENTRE FOR
FUNCTIONAL ECOLOGY
SCIENCE FOR PEOPLE & THE PLANET

MUSHROOMS IN THE CITY

A @cfe_micolab initiative

How to register your findings and
help map Coimbra's mushroom
diversity.

THE DIFFERENT PARTS OF A MUSHROOM

The most commonly recognised mushrooms have a stem and a cap. In these species, the hymenophore (the structure that bears the surface where spores are produced) is located underneath the cap and the stem may have a ring and/or a structure at the base known as the volva. The hymenophore is often made up of gills, but we can easily find variations, like tubes (which look like pores from below) or teeth-like structures. To identify a mushroom all of these characteristics need to be taken into account.

In your search for mushrooms, however, you will also come across very different shapes, from shelf-like brackets growing on trees to tiny cups on the ground, among many others.

DOWNLOAD THE INATURALIST APP

- You can register online on [iNaturalist.org](https://www.inaturalist.org) or download the mobile app.
- Go to settings to join the iNaturalist Portuguese network Biodiversity4All.
- Scan this QR code for more information.

WHAT TO BRING WITH YOU ?

- A camera or smartphone, preferably with GPS turned on to automatically record the date and location of the photo.
- A knife to remove and cut the mushroom.
- A pencil, ruler or coin to use as a scale in the photo (alternatively, you can photograph the mushroom in your hand).

HOW TO PHOTOGRAPH MUSHROOMS

- Ensure that the photos are focused and have sufficient quality to zoom-in.
- Take a photo of the mushroom with its habitat and substrate visible.
- Photograph various details, such as the cap, the stem, and underneath the cap. You can add multiple photos to your record.
- Use an object for scale in the photo.
- Avoid using the camera flash, as it may lead to changes in the mushroom's color in the photo.

OTHER USEFUL DETAILS

- Cut the mushroom longitudinally to observe the attachment of the hymenium to the stem, color changes (such as the appearance of a blue color in some boletes) or latex exudation (common in *Lactarius* species).
- Photograph the spores if you come across a deposit on leaves or other mushrooms.

WHAT TO ADD TO THE NOTES SECTION

- Details that can not be captured in the photographs, such as any distinctive odor or texture.
- In the case of color changes or latex exudation, register whether it was a rapid or slow change, or if there were changes in the colour of the latex.
- The substrate where the mushroom is growing (soil, leaves, wood, etc.).
- Whether it is isolated or growing in a group.
- The nearby trees, as some mushrooms form associations with specific groups of plants.

DON'T FORGET!

- You can touch the mushrooms without fear, but never eat them without being absolutely certain of their identification.
- If possible, leave the mushrooms as you found them so they can continue to release their spores.
- Be careful not to damage other mushrooms or trample the ground too much.
- Avoid removing all or most mushrooms from one location, especially the younger ones.